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BUILDING CAPACITY OF TEACHERS/FACILITATORS IN TECHNOLOGY-PEDAGOGY INTEGRATION FOR IMPROVED TEACHING AND LEARNING

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Abstract

Competent teachers apply broad set of knowledge to plan their instruction. Technology proficiency is an important dimension in this preparation. The introduction of technology causes the representation of new concepts and requires developing sensitivity to the dynamic, transactional relationship between all three components namely content, technology and pedagogy. Integrating technology into the classroom has become an imperative for teachers at all levels. Mostly all schools today have computer labs or a computer in the classroom. Many also have internet connections. This paper is an attempt to explain integration of technology and pedagogy in teacher education.

Teacher education aims at developing skills and appropriate knowledge among teacher trainees for using and integrating the correct technology in an appropriate manner. Every teacher should know how to use technology, pedagogy and subject area content effectively in their daily classroom teaching. Merely introducing technology to the educational process is not enough. One must ensure technological integration since technology by itself will not lead to any change. Rather, it is the way in which teachers integrate technology that has the potential to bring change in the education process. Teachers must understand their role in technologically-oriented classrooms.

Good teaching is not simply adding technology to the existing teaching and content domain. Rather, the introduction of technology causes the representation of new concepts and requires developing sensitivity to the dynamic, transactional relationship between all three components namely content, technology and pedagogy (Koehler and Mishra, 2005). Preparing teachers to use technology effectively is a major area of concern for teacher education. Effective technology use includes such activities as linking curriculum outcomes with various technologies, establishing a learning context of discovery and process in the use of technology, collaborating with others both face-to-face and virtually to achieve learning outcomes, simulating real-world environments, and assessing outcomes.

Techno-pedagogy demands that life-world experience be entangled in hyper-learning. It is a key factor in deciding whether an educational media product is successful or not. Techno-pedagogy refers to weaving the techniques of the craft of teaching into the learning

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environment itself. It requires conscious recognition of the mediated learning environment in order to maximize the ease and clarity in the transmission of information.

Pre-service teachers should have techno-pedagogic skills but as a matter of fact, it has been revealed that in-service teachers hesitate to use ICT in education due to lack of time and motivation. The reason for lack of motivation lies in their teacher -training module, which is devoid of ICT element. This kind of situation does not equip student teacher with a required set of confidence which is necessary to include ICT in normal classroom teaching. There is a need to train our student teacher in such a way that they should be able to work with different type of school environment and devise new methods of teaching with ICT use. Such kind of instruction is also useful in attaining higher objectives of education like increasing classroom transaction, reducing drop out ratio, full utilization of resources etc. It is obvious that at this level, we are not concerned with ICT literacy which we found more or less present in every pre-service teacher. At this particular point we are struggling to solve problems like: when and where to use ICT, which type of technology is appropriate, is it justified (not merely sake of using, it should be relevant also), how to use internet etc. Such situation clearly indicates pre-service teacher's unawareness about different planning and implementation strategies for using ICT in education.

Teachers are already skilled instructional facilitators and reflective practitioners as they know how to plan, prepare and implement instructional strategies. Addition of technological skills, help them to become technologically competent as well. And such competency has become necessary to face the challenge of information world to education sector. In recent years the information world has put pressure on academic world by its speedy, effective and communication of knowledge by creating new foundations to work as a team by providing facilities like access to variety of learning resources, collaborative learning, immediacy to information, multimedia approach to education, authentic and up to date information, online library, distance learning, better access to children with special needs, creating online learning environment etc.

Earlier technology was used to teach student about technology, now our concern is not only to provide knowledge, but to enable student teachers towards integrating it in their instructional design. This need can be fulfilled if we provide such situations to our pre-service teachers, where they can practically think about teaching and planning for instruction in accordance with the specific needs of learners. This will enable them to think about technology integration from the perspective of both the teacher and learner. In such a situation a teacher is aware of sources and characteristics of the student's misconceptions and hence productive change can be brought about. In this phenomenon pre-service teacher may realize that effective and meaningful teaching with technology does not require a teacher to be a computer expert but requires insight to use it appropriately and the focus remains on the processes of learning- both about technology and the implementation of that technology to improve teaching and

student learning. Implementing technology effectively requires linking curriculum outcomes with various technologies, establishing a learning context of discovery and process in the use of technology, collaborating with others face to face and virtually to learning outcomes, simulating real-world environments and assessing outcomes (Zaidi, 2012). To develop an understanding about processes of teaching with technology helps student teachers to become techno-pedagogically skilled teachers as it opens new and different forms of knowledge that can be fostered by instructional use of technology.

Pre-service teachers should be helped in gaining real life experience regarding technology integration by exposing them towards virtual field trips of classroom and lab protocol etc. Such technology exposure helps them to question about their doubts regarding enhancement to teaching learning, enrichment of students learning experiences and involvement of students influenced by the infusion of technology. To successfully infuse technology into pedagogy, students need to become critical and reflective thinker as well. Also it is necessary to make them aware of the fact that we are living in a culture of constantly changing technology by every passing day. Today we are dealing with the technology, may be replaced completely by newer one tomorrow. So every time, teachers have to make continual decisions about how to best utilize these tools in teaching- learning and assessment.

It is becoming increasingly clear that merely introducing technology to the educational process is not enough to ensure technology integration since technology alone does not lead to change. Rather, it is the way in which teachers use technology that has the potential to change education (Carr *et al.*, 1998). For teachers to become fluent with educational technology, means going beyond mere competence with the latest tools (Zhao, 2003), to develop an understanding of the complex web of relationships between users, technologies, practices, and tools.

Research works of (Angeli and Valannides, 2009; PanAfrican Research Agenda on the Pedagogical Integration of ICTs 2011) have shown that in spite of the many efforts that researchers and educators put over the years in preparing teachers in the educational uses of technology, teachers still lack the skills and knowledge needed to be able to teach with technology successfully. The reasons of failure to prepare teachers to teach with technology can be attributed to:

1. More emphasis on the acquisition of technical skills, which are taught in isolation from a subject-specific context.
2. The lack of a subject-specific pedagogical focus in many technology preparation programs, resultant of which the teachers remain unable to establish pedagogical connections between the affordances of technology and the teaching of a particular content domain.
3. The lack of national policy for teacher training in the pedagogical integration of ICT and the lack of theory and conceptual frameworks to inform and guide research and actions in

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the area of teaching with technology, as theoretical framework about teaching with technology is needed to provide our everyday classroom efforts, a direction and meaning.

4. Lack of incentive plans for teachers discourages pedagogical integration of ICT in teaching. Incentive plans such as (promotions of teachers, low-interest loans to teachers so that they buy equipments, etc.) can be introduced.
5. Absence of techno-pedagogical resource banks specific to our education system demotivate teachers to use technology as they don't have time to search for and assess the vast quantity of resources available on the Internet.

Effective ICT integration undoubtedly promotes better academic results. To integrate ICT effectively, teachers have to develop an approach which is a combination of content, pedagogy and technology. The specialized, highly applied knowledge that supports content-based technology integration is known as "technological pedagogical content knowledge," abbreviated TPCK or TPACK (Koehler & Mishra, 2008). TPACK is the intersection of teachers' knowledge of curriculum content, general pedagogies, and technologies (see Fig.1).

Figure 1: Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (Koehler & Mishra, 2008)

TPACK (appearing in the centre of Fig. 1) is knowledge that results from teachers' concurrent and interdependent content, general pedagogy, and technology understanding, it is comprised, in part, by three particular aspects of that knowledge that are represented by the other three intersections depicted (Harris & Hofer, 2009). These are:

- *Pedagogical Content Knowledge*: How to teach particular content-based material
- *Technological Content Knowledge*: How to select and use technologies to communicate particular content knowledge
- *Technological Pedagogical Knowledge*: How to use particular technologies while teaching.
- *Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge*: Knowledge of the complex interaction among the principle knowledge domains (content, Pedagogy, technology).

The TPACK framework articulates the role of technology in the process of teaching and learning in a truly integrated manner. As Koehler and Mishra (2009) argue, the concept of TPACK “allows teachers, researchers, and teacher educators to move beyond oversimplified approaches that treat technology as an ‘add-on’ instead to focus again, and in a more ecological way, upon the connections among technology, content, and pedagogy as they play out in classroom contexts” (p. 67).

TPACK can be viewed as a model for planning instruction that incorporates systematic and judicious selection of technologies and teaching/learning strategies. In such type of model, a curriculum-specific, technology-enhanced learning *activity types* are used as the building blocks for instructional planning. Each activity type describes plans for learning experience and captures what is most essential about the structure of a particular kind of learning action as it relates to *what students do* when engaged in that particular learning-related activity like group discussion. Group discussion in small to large groups, students engage in dialogue with their peers and for this the possible technology can be blackboard, discussion in Wiki spaces. Similarly for an activity type of presentation, students share their understanding with others; oral or multimedia approach and possible technology choice can be PowerPoint or Moviemaker. For an activity type where students need to engage in civic action, students write government representatives or engage in some other form of civic action, the possible technology can be email or videoconferencing.

Similarly various activity types are developed along with their possible technology. When teachers are familiar with a complete set of technology-enriched learning activity types in a particular curriculum area, they can effectively choose among, combine, and use them in standards-based learning situations, building their TPACK in practical ways while doing so. This differs substantially from how teachers typically learn to integrate educational technologies into their teaching. In the activity types approach, educational technology selections are not made until curriculum-based learning goals and activity designs are finalized.

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By selecting the technologies that best serve learning goals and activities *last*, both students' learning and maximally appropriate educational technology uses are assured. Such kind of planning focuses upon student's curriculum -based learning rather based on selecting technological tools.

Conclusion

It is a challenge to plan curriculum-based learning integrated with appropriate and pedagogically powerful educational technology for students. For this a detailed and deliberated planning is needed, which above activity types provide us. Through such activity types we can choose among a full range of possible educational activities that incorporate technology powerfully. Such a model helps us to focus more upon use of most appropriate for a particular group of students within a particular educational context. Alternately, if learning goals have been selected well, if pedagogical decisions have been made according to students' instructional and contextual realities, and if activity types and assessment strategies have been selected to address those goals and realities, then choices of instructionally appropriate tools and resources to use in the learning experience being planned are more obvious and straightforward. One of the aspects of technological pedagogical knowledge is the familiarity of teachers with available tools' instructional affordances and constraints. This approach is designed to help teachers to plan effective, efficient, and engaging learning experiences for their students. The process is based upon a series of deliberate, balanced, and well-informed pedagogical choices, which, when taken together, can result in an instructionally effective plan for students' learning that incorporates digital and non-digital tools and resources in appropriate ways. Activity-based instructional planning strategies are unique contribution of TPACK development method.

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